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FORMATION OF PSYCHOLOGICAL SPACE AS A FACTOR OF SUCCESSFUL ADAPTATION TO SCHOOL OF CHILDREN WITH SPEECH DISORDERS

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The essence and significance of the formation of psychological space as a factor of successful adaptation to school of children with speech disorders are analyzed. It is determined, that the violation of the child's psychological space causes a painful attitude to everything around and contributes to the formation of internal psychological conflict, which inevitably leads to loss of learning motivation, reduced cognitive activity, disrupted relationships with teachers and peers. The aim is to prove that the formation of psychological space will contribute to the successful adaptation of children with speech disorders to study in primary education.

The methods of research of the outlined problem are theoretical methods that allowed to separate the provisions that needed to be verified. Empirical methods allowed to identify the level of adaptability of children to study in an educational institution, among them: observation, conversation, testing, statement experiment, processing of research results (presented as a percentage).

It was found, that psychological space, a sense of comfort, safety is one of the most important areas of human life, and a properly constructed psychological space can provide a sense of security in the school environment during the period of adaptation. It is noted, that in order to facilitate the adaptation of children to learning, in the primary level should be a deep and expanded diagnosis of readiness for learning activities and preparatory work with children who have insufficient school adaptation.

The diagnostic procedure and the program of research of psychological space as a factor of successful adaptation to school of children with speech disorders are described. The conditions of formation of personal space of a junior school-child are defined. It is concluded, that the purposeful formation of psychological space makes it possible to ensure the success of the process of adaptation to learning at school. Psychological space, a sense of comfort, security is one of the most important areas of human life and from the first days of children's schooling, a teacher must ensure that school attendance for a child is not burdensome, form a cognitive learning motive that would dominate in the future studying

Keywords: *psychological space, adaptation, speech disorders, children with speech disorders*

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1. Introduction

One of the problems at the stage of development of the education system is the issue of adaptation and socialization of children with disabilities. This problem is even more relevant for children with speech disorders, the process of adaptation and socialization of which is carried out with significant difficulties due to the peculiarities of development. Promoting the adaptation of a child with speech disorders is, first of all, the optimization of new environmental conditions. Upon entering the school, the child is presented with a system of externally regulated requirements, ie he/she is expected to have certain abilities, skills, knowledge necessary for his/her participation in educational activities, communication with classmates and teachers.

The child feels confident when he/she has adequate opportunities to meet all external requirements and when psychological boundaries and feelings of security are maintained. Only then will he/she experience the emotional satisfaction of being in school. That is, we are talking about the socio-psychological aspect of adaptation,

which is a fairly accurate indicator of various developmental disorders, formed in a child in preschool age.

It is known, that the number of children with speech disorders is constantly increasing. This puts psychologists and educators in need of further search for new effective methods to facilitate the adaptation of such students to school.

2. Literary review

Adaptation to school life is understood as adjusting to new conditions of communication and implementing new specific rules, requirements and subjects, related to educational activities [1–3].

Considering the concept of "adaptation of children to school", we talk about the process of getting used to the child's new environment, operating conditions, procedures, requirements, etc. [4]. Studies have identified and described high, medium and low levels of school adaptation [5].

The system of the child's relations with him/herself and the world begins to take shape in the

primary school, and educational attitudes that become basic and stable forms of relationships with peers and adults determine the further success of the child's schooling, opportunities for personal self-realization. Thus, the effectiveness of the child's adaptation to learning in primary education determines the effectiveness of further stay and education of the child in education [6, 7].

There is a large amount of research on the problem of adaptation to school of children with and without psychophysical development peculiarities. Attention is paid to children with impaired vision, hearing, musculoskeletal system, intelligence and mental retardation. As for children with speech disorders, such studies are much less [8–10]. Note that the study does not cover the problem of the impact of psychological space as a factor in the successful adaptation of children to study in an educational institution.

3. The aim and objectives of the study

The aim of the article is to prove that the formation of psychological space will contribute to the successful adaptation of children with speech disorders to study in primary education.

To achieve this goal, the following tasks were set:

1. To substantiate the importance and influence of psychological space on the process of adaptation of children with speech disorders to study in primary education.
2. To identify the features of adaptation to school of children with various speech disorders.
3. To present the structure of the program of educational and developmental training for the formation of psychological space in children with speech disorders.

4. Materials and methods

Theoretical research methods were used, which allowed to separate the provisions that needed to be verified. Empirical methods were also used to determine the level of children's adaptability to study in an educational institution. Among them: test interviews, proposed by S. Bankov to determine the degree of psychosocial maturity; Kern-Jirasek test to determine the level of intelligence and school maturity. In particular, research on environmental orientation, knowledge, social maturity, attitudes towards schooling; mental (logic, attention, visual perception, thinking, speech, memory, imagery) and speech development; proofreading tests to determine the level of mental capacity; test of evaluation of speech features in the system of personal relations according to R. Erickson.

5. Research results and discussion

If we talk about the concept of "sovereignty of psychological space", it was introduced by S. Nartova-Bochaver. In particular, the author suggested that the study of a fragment of reality significant for the individual environment, in our case the school environment, determines the strategies and current tactics of personal behavior and includes a set of physical, social, psychological phenomena. Therefore, we think it is appropriate to consider an individual as a psycho-spatial phenomenon, within which the key concepts are "psychological space" and "psychological sovereignty" of the person, which is an important indicator of psychological health and a condition for adaptation processes [11].

In a broad sense, the concept of "psychological space" is revealed from two sides of human life – the individuality of an individual and interaction in society. Also, the psychological space can be represented in the form of a specific area, which to some extent determines the essence of events, taking place in it. S. Nartova-Bochaver considers sovereignty a systemic feature of personality, a necessary condition for normal functioning and development [11].

Thus, the degree and peculiarities of adaptation, the intensity of negative physiological changes, the level of psychological stress depend on the characteristics of the environment (family situation, class size, pedagogical style of a teacher, type of curriculum) and individual personality traits of a child (nervous system type, psychophysiological maturity, physical and mental health, communicative competence, level of preschool training, etc.) [1, 9].

An indicator of difficulties of the process of adaptation to school is negative changes in the child's behavior: it can be excessive arousal, even aggression, or, conversely, inhibition and depression. Feelings of fear, reluctance to go to school, etc. may occur. Characteristic of children of primary school age are the following reactions of psychological protection: 1) active protest (hostility); 2) passive protest (avoidance); 3) anxiety and self-doubt. These variants of maladaptive behavior include negative manifestations in all areas of child's activities at school.

Child's problems in speech development create the basis for obstacles in the development of his/her communication with others, in establishing broad social ties, when the "normal growth of a child in culture" is disrupted [9].

Thus, children with speech disorders are usually unsuccessful among their peers, as a result of which the personal aspect of adaptation suffers. Being a rejected team, the child does not want to attend school, as a result, he/she may develop a negative attitude towards school, class, teachers.

From the beginning of school, students seek to join the system of collective relationships, which is associated with the growing need to communicate with peers, the desire to participate in collective activities, to find their place in collective relations, to be recognized as peers, despite individual differences, in particular speech disorders. However, due to certain problems and speech disorders, there is a discrepancy between the desires and the actual state of this process.

Therefore, studying the problems of adaptation to the education of older preschool children with speech disorders, we can conclude that this adaptation is determined not only by the amount of knowledge, abilities, masteries, but also skills: to analyze, compare, summarize, systematize and express all this in clear speech. This is the basis of conscious assimilation of knowledge and mental development.

We believe that in order to preserve the intrinsic value of childhood and facilitate adaptation to schooling in primary school, it is necessary to conduct an expanded and in-depth diagnosis of the child's readiness for learning. It is worth noting, that children who successfully adapted to school life in the 1st grade, later showed the effectiveness of tasks, set before them, experienced satisfaction with their

success and usually demonstrated success throughout the period of study at the institution. In case of insufficient level of school adaptation, preparatory work with children is mandatory, aimed at the development of mental abilities and purposeful formation of psychological space, which allows to ensure the success of the process of adaptation to learning in educational institutions.

The study of the peculiarities of adaptation to learning was based on a diagnostic program that was tested among 30 older preschool children with speech disorders who entered the first grades. The qualitative and quantitative analysis of the results of the study showed that children with speech disorders have mostly low and medium levels of adaptation and more often than their peers have difficulty, communicating with teachers and adults; they are frightened even by the thought of the need to speak in public; they do not like to be the initiator of acquaintances with each other; it is difficult for the children to speak in front of the class; they do not like public appearances; they are willing to communicate with only a few comrades; when speaking often feel nervous; difficult to tolerate meetings with new people; they often refuse to answer questions, even when they know the answer, because they are afraid to speak.

Suppose that successful adaptation can be helped by working on the psychological space of the student. To do this, we have developed a training program, aimed at updating the components of the psychological space.

We take into account the approach of S. Nartova-Bochaver, who defines psychological sovereignty as the ability of a person to control, protect and develop their psychological space, based on the general experience of successful autonomous behavior; as a form of subjectivity, which in various forms of activity allows to realize human needs [11]. As mentioned above, the structural components of sovereignty include the dimensions of psychological space: the sovereignty of the physical body, territory, things, habits, social ties, values. Psychological sovereignty can be studied only through the above dimensions of psychological space.

The structure of the program of educational and developmental training "Formation of personal space of junior schoolchildren":

The block of actualization of integrity of personal space.

Exercises aimed at:

- forming a positive attitude to the organization of their body;
- discovering and forming an attitude to one's own health;
- forming the skills of organizing "their place" in the real environment (home, class, workplace, etc.); manifestation of individuality through things, clothes;
- overcoming feelings of uncertainty.

This unit offers exercises, such as "Me and my name", "First impression", "Silent greeting", "Couple communication", "Recognize me", "Let's grow tall", "My body". A discussion was held on the topic "My house is my fortress". Picture "Fear that prevents you from being confident." This includes the task of organizing a "workplace" (it was allowed to bring from home something that would create a feeling of comfort while at school).

The block of actualization of self-organization of personal space - is responsible for the development of identification activity in interaction with the world of things, people and social phenomena.

Regarding the implementation of the tasks of this block it is necessary:

- to form the need for self-development of students, their motivation to perform various activities,
- to actualize the value-semantic attitude to the cognitive sphere and social activity of students.

Among the exercises used were ones for positive self-perception, "My positive qualities", "My strengths". Also in the classes of this stage a number of situations were performed and played out, aimed at developing flexibility of thinking, getting rid of social attitudes and stereotypes, correcting the conservative value system and forming cognitive schemes that reflect social values and ideals.

The block of actualization of openness of personal space – is responsible for the formation of a conscious position on personal-behavioral self-disclosure.

The purpose of this block of the program was to develop tolerance and dialogic orientation in communication, which involves the implementation of tasks aimed at:

- preservation of personal boundaries when interacting with people;
- communicativeness;
- expansion of social contacts;
- manifestation of one's own position in interaction with people.

In the class, students performed a number of exercises, including "Broken Phone", which aimed to teach active listening skills, "Different Answers", aimed at building the ability to argue their own point of view, "Earthquake", which aimed at developing compromise skills, "Contact", aimed at achieving openness and trust in communication.

Thus, the proposed training sessions allowed to carry out educational and developmental work on the construction of personal space of students.

The change in the results and the dynamics of readiness for school among students with speech disorders can be seen in the diagram (Fig. 1).

Fig. 1. Dynamics of readiness for school among students with speech disorders

The results of the re-study show high-level changes and low-level decrease, which is evidence of the effectiveness of the training program for successful adaptation to learning of children with speech disorders.

The study does not cover all aspects of solving the problem of forming psychological space as a factor in suc-

successful adaptation to learning of children with speech disorders. In particular, the study covered only children of one nosology. Based on this, the prospect of further research is to find effective ways to form a psychological space as a factor in the successful adaptation of children with special educational needs of other nosologies to study in an inclusive primary education institution.

6. Conclusions

1. Psychological space, a sense of comfort, security is one of the most important areas of human life. Properly constructed psychological space can provide a sense of security in primary school during the period of adaptation. Therefore, from the first days of children's stay in an educational institution, a teacher must take care to create conditions that would promote the formation of a cognitive motive for learning, which will be dominant in further activities of a student.

2. The analysis of theoretical sources and the observational experiment allow us to draw certain conclusions about the peculiarities of adaptation of children with speech disorders to study in primary education institutions. In particular, children of this category have some difficulties in communicating with teachers, adults; afraid to speak in public or in front of the class; do not like to get to know each other; they find it difficult to communicate when meeting new people; due to phonetic disorders have difficulty, pronouncing some words; feel anxious when they understand the need to speak; they often cannot answer, even when they know the answer to the question. In addition, 35–

55 % of them show low efficiency, negative emotional background, low level of attention, somatic weakness, reduced CNS functionality, lack of productivity.

3. Based on the above, it was concluded, that it is necessary to take measures to form the personal space of applicants of primary school age. The most effective for the formation of psychological space is the use of educational and developmental training. The structure of the training includes blocks, related to the actualization of: the integrity of personal space; self-organization of personal space, for the development of identification activity in interaction with the environment; openness of personal space, which is responsible for the formation of a conscious position, the development of tolerance and dialogic orientation in communication. In addition, it is important to form a positive attitude to the organization of their body, identify and form an attitude to their own health, the formation of skills to organize "their place" in the real environment (home, class, workplace, etc.); manifestation of individuality through things, clothes, overcoming feelings of uncertainty, forming the need for self-development of students, their motivation to perform various activities, actualization of the value-semantic attitude to the cognitive sphere and social activity of students. It is also necessary to develop communication skills, the ability to expand social contacts, the manifestation of their own position in interaction with people.

Conflicts of interest

The authors declare that they have no conflicts of interest.

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